

Decomposition of 2-norms

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Abstract.

In this paper, after introducing the notion of asymmetric semi 2-norm and asymmetric 2-norm, we present the conjugate function of an asymmetric 2-norm. Then we give a decomposition of a 2-norm in two conjugated asymmetric 2-norms.

Keywords: Asymmetric semi 2-norm; conjugate function of an asymmetric 2-norm; decomposition of a 2-norm.

1. Introduction

In 1968 Duffin and Karlovitz [1] proposed the term asymmetric semi norm when the property of symmetry is not satisfied in a semi norm. Many classical results of the analysis have been extended to such non-symmetric spaces as in [2],[3].

Let first give the definition of the asymmetric 2-norm function.

Definition1.1. Let X be an vectorial space. The function $\|.,.\|: X^2 \rightarrow R^+$ it is called the asymmetric 2-norm function if:

- 1) $\|x, x\| \geq 0$ for $\forall x \in X$ and $\|x, x\| = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = 0$
- 2) $\|x, y\| = \|y, x\|$ for $x, y \in X$
- 3) $\|\lambda x, y\| = \lambda \|x, y\|$ for $\lambda > 0$ and $x, y \in X$
- 4) $\|x + y, z\| \leq \|x, z\| + \|y, z\|$ for $x, y, z \in X$.

The pair $(X, \|.,.\|)$ is then called an asymmetric 2-normed space.

Example1.2. Let $X = R$ and $p(x): R \rightarrow R^+$ an asymmetric norm on R , (defined in [4]). For every two points $x(x_1, x_2)$ and $y(y_1, y_2)$ on R^2 we remark: $\|x, y\| = p(x_1)p(y_1) + p(x_2)p(y_2)$.

Claim1.3. The function $\|x, y\| = p(x_1)p(y_1) + p(x_2)p(y_2)$ is an asymmetric 2-norm function on R .

Proof:

- 1) $\|x, x\| \geq 0$ for $\forall x \in X$ and $\|x, x\| = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = 0$
 $\|x, x\| = p(x_1)p(x_1) + p(x_2)p(x_2) = p^2(x_1) + p^2(x_2) > 0$
 $\|x, x\| = 0 \Leftrightarrow p^2(x_1) + p^2(x_2) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x_1 = x_2 = 0$ for $\forall x \in X$.
- 2) $\|x, y\| = \|y, x\|$ for $x, y \in X$
 $\|x, y\| = p(x_1)p(y_1) + p(x_2)p(y_2) = p(y_1)p(x_1) + p(y_2)p(x_2) = \|y, x\|$

- 3) $\|\lambda x, y\| = \lambda \|x, y\|$ for $\lambda > 0$ and $x, y \in X$
 $\|\lambda x, y\| = p(\lambda x_1)p(y_1) + p(\lambda x_2)p(y_2) = \lambda [p(x_1)p(y_1) + p(x_2)p(y_2)] = \lambda \|x, y\|$
- 4) $\|x + y, z\| \leq \|x, z\| + \|y, z\|$ for $x, y, z \in X$
 $\|x + y, z\| = p(x_1 + y_1)p(z_1) + p(x_2 + y_2)p(z_2) \leq [p(x_1) + p(y_1)]p(z_1) + [p(x_2) + p(y_2)]p(z_2) =$
 $= p(x_1)p(z_1) + p(x_2)p(z_2) + p(y_1)p(z_1) + p(y_2)p(z_2) = \|x, z\| + \|y, z\|.$ ■

Definition 1.4. The function $\sigma : X^2 \rightarrow R^+$ is called an asymmetric semi 2-norm if:

- 1) $\sigma(x, y) = 0$ if x, y linearly dependent
- 2) $\sigma(x, y) = \sigma(y, x)$ for every $x, y \in X$
- 3) $\sigma(\lambda x, y) = \lambda \sigma(x, y)$, for $\lambda > 0$
- 4) $\sigma(x, y) = \sigma(x, y - x)$ for every $x, y \in X$.

The analogue definition of the semi 2-norm and 2-norm function is given in [4].

2. Main results

Now the conjugate of the asymmetric semi 2-norm function is defined by:

$$\bar{\sigma}(x, y) = \sigma(-x, -y), \quad x, y \in X.$$

The function $\sigma^s : X^2 \rightarrow R^+$ given by:

$$\sigma^s(x, y) = \max \{ \sigma(x, y), \bar{\sigma}(x, y) \}, \quad x, y \in X$$

is an asymmetric semi 2-norm [5].

An asymmetric semi 2-norm σ on X^2 is an asymmetric 2-norm if only if σ^s is a 2-norm on X .

Definition 2.1. If $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$ is a 2-norm on and $\sigma \neq \|\cdot, \cdot\|$ is an asymmetric 2-norm such that $\sigma^s = \|\cdot, \cdot\|$ then the pair (σ, σ^s) is called a decomposition of the 2-norm $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$.

Theorem 2.2. Let $(X^2, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ be a 2-normed space. For each $f : X \rightarrow R$ linear function and each $k \geq 1$ there exist a decomposition of $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$.

Proof. Given such f, k , we define $\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \|x, y\|, & f(x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\|x, y\|}{k}, & f(x) < 0 \end{cases}$.

Let's prove $\sigma_{f,k}(x, y)$ is an asymmetric 2-norm.

- 1) It is clear that: $\sigma_{f,k}(x, x) = \begin{cases} \|x, x\|, & f(x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\|x, x\|}{k}, & f(x) < 0 \end{cases}$. So $\sigma_{f,k}(x, x) \geq 0$ and $\sigma_{f,k}(x, x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = 0$.

$$2) \quad \sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \|x, y\|, f(x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\|x, y\|}{k}, f(x) < 0 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \|y, x\|, f(x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\|y, x\|}{k}, f(x) < 0 \end{cases} = \sigma_{f,k}(y, x).$$

3) For $\lambda > 0$ we have:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(\lambda x, y) = \begin{cases} \|\lambda x, y\|, f(x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\|\lambda x, y\|}{k}, f(x) < 0 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \lambda \|x, y\|, f(x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\lambda \|x, y\|}{k}, f(x) < 0 \end{cases} = \lambda \sigma_{f,k}(x, y).$$

4) For the triangle inequality we have 4 cases for $x, y, z \in X$.

Case 1. If $f(x) \geq 0$ and $f(y) \geq 0$ then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x+y, z) = \|x+y, z\| \leq \|x, z\| + \|y, z\| = \sigma_{f,k}(x, z) + \sigma_{f,k}(y, z).$$

Case 2. If $f(x) < 0$ and $f(y) < 0$ then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x+y, z) = \frac{\|x+y, z\|}{k} \leq \frac{\|x, z\| + \|y, z\|}{k} = \frac{\|x, z\|}{k} + \frac{\|y, z\|}{k} = \sigma_{f,k}(x, z) + \sigma_{f,k}(y, z).$$

Case 3. If $f(x) \geq 0$ and $f(y) < 0$, in this case we have two possibilities:

1) $f(x+y) \geq 0$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{f,k}(x+y, z) &= \|x+y, z\| \leq \|x, z\| + \|y, z\| = \sigma_{f,k}(x, z) + k\sigma_{f,k}(y, z) \leq \\ &\leq k(\sigma_{f,k}(x, z) + \sigma_{f,k}(y, z)) = \sigma_{f,k}(x, z) + \sigma_{f,k}(y, z) \text{ for } k=1. \end{aligned}$$

2) $f(x+y) < 0$, then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x+y, z) = \frac{\|x+y, z\|}{k} \leq \frac{\|x, z\| + \|y, z\|}{k} \leq \|x, z\| + \frac{\|y, z\|}{k} = \sigma_{f,k}(x, z) + \sigma_{f,k}(y, z).$$

Case 4. If $f(x) < 0$ and $f(y) \geq 0$ is treated similarly to case 3.

Now it remains to prove that $\sigma_{f,k}^s = \|\cdot, \cdot\|$. In order to do this let us identify $\bar{\sigma}_{f,k}$:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,k}(x, y) = \sigma_{f,k}(-x, -y) = \begin{cases} \|-x, -y\|, f(-x) \geq 0 \\ \frac{\|-x, -y\|}{k}, f(-x) < 0 \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \|x, y\|, f(x) \leq 0 \\ \frac{\|x, y\|}{k}, f(x) > 0 \end{cases}$$

therefore: $\sigma_{f,k}^s = \max\{\sigma_{f,k}(x, y), \bar{\sigma}_{f,k}(x, y)\} = \|x, y\|$. ■

Theorem 2.3. Let $(X^2, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ be an 2-normed space and f, g be functions as in Theorem 2.2 and $k, l \geq 1$. Then:

$$\sigma_{f,k} \equiv \sigma_{g,l}.$$

Proof. Let $x, y \in X$ and assume $k < l$. By Theorem 2.2 there exist $\sigma_{f,k}$ and $\sigma_{g,l}$.

Case 1. If $f(x) \geq 0$ and $g(x) \geq 0$, then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \|x, y\| = \sigma_{g,l}(x, y).$$

Case 2. If $f(x) < 0$ and $g(x) < 0$, then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \frac{\|x, y\|}{k} > \frac{\|x, y\|}{l} = \sigma_{g,l}(x, y).$$

Case 3. If $f(x) \geq 0$ and $g(x) < 0$, then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \|x, y\| > \frac{\|x, y\|}{l} = \sigma_{g,l}(x, y).$$

Case 4. If $f(x) < 0$ and $g(x) \geq 0$, then:

$$\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \frac{\|x, y\|}{k} < \|x, y\| = \sigma_{g,l}(x, y).$$

So $k\sigma_{f,k}(x, y)$ satisfies for cases 1,2 and 3 that $k\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) \geq \sigma_{g,l}(x, y)$, and case 4 that $k\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) = \sigma_{g,l}(x, y)$. Likewise $l\sigma_{g,l}(x, y)$ satisfies for cases 1,2 and 4 that $l\sigma_{g,l}(x, y) \geq \sigma_{f,k}(x, y)$ and case 3 that $l\sigma_{g,l}(x, y) = \sigma_{f,k}(x, y)$, i.e. $k\sigma_{f,k}(x, y) \geq \sigma_{g,l}(x, y)$ and $l\sigma_{g,l}(x, y) \geq \sigma_{f,k}(x, y)$ for all $x \in X$. This is $\sigma_{f,k} \equiv \sigma_{g,l}$. ■

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